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ENTREPRENEUR STUDENT WITHIN AN ACADEMIC STARTUP GARAGE

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ABSTRACT

Startup Garage is an education and training space, aimed at interaction between students, lecturers and companies, by jointly creating a formative laboratory, tailor-made to nurture cross-fertilization focusing on entrepreneurial ideas. The main objective is to formulate new products and resolve any problems which may emerge with innovation and professionalism. Lecturers and external experts have a defined role, and as such they give scientific, technical and professional support. An IT platform (Pingel@p) assists with the collection and assessment of the students' ideas and in particular matches the student with stand-by mentors. Thanks to Pingel@p, the collection and evaluation system of ideas may be opened to high school pupils and their teachers. Furthermore, an extracurricular training attributes 3 ECTS to a course called "The enterprise of an idea", in which idea owners learn actively together with mentors and company employees in a cooperative way, thus transmitting reciprocal abilities: creativity, innovation, passion, organization and managerial skills. Consequently, students acquire managerial tools and employees the entrepreneurial attitude. Final goal is to create a large and secure network of stakeholders in which students are principal actors. Entrepreneurial students are advised by active mentors; students in the Garage "call for expertise" of other skilled students to help them enhance their ideas; companies ask students to solve problems through a "call for needs resolution"; all in order to implement ideas in a safe environment where IP is going to be protected by Blockchain technology.

1 INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship education is becoming more relevant, enough to feed a current discussion about considering entrepreneurship a specific area of knowledge [1]. Many students look for extracurricular opportunities to apply theoretical knowledge to something they really want to do. They are ready to take additional classes to learn more how to succeed in business.

Millennial entrepreneurs do not want to get a degree giving themselves the chance to find a job, instead they seek a way to succeed as an entrepreneur. That explains partly why business incubators are booming among university lately, with many top research institutions

establishing incubators and bragging about their ability to help move innovation out of the ivory tower and into the marketplace [2]. Although many University-linked Business Incubators and Accelerators are far from being in a profitable situation to collect money, today we must envisage and recognize additional threats in advance: university incubators and technology transfer offices must deal with very limited budgets and revenue coming from patent licensing. Nevertheless, according to an inquiry, University incubated businesses created more jobs and generated more sales than those incubated elsewhere [3].

We have passed through some innovation pattern that was formed initially by two recognizable drivers, government and industry – Mode 2 – and which has evolved into an intertwined relationship among university–industry–government – The Triple Helix – [4]. Today, we are facing with a new digital pattern more systematically interconnected thus forming a quadruple helix model featured by partnership involving **government, industry, academia and civil participants** in the open innovation process [5]. In this new innovation dynamic, open innovation model will modify and form a new paradigm to drive innovation in the future.

Not so long ago students were considered as passive actors within “The triple Helix”. The students were there to study and the teachers to accomplish their duties. Students were treated as academic participants and not as active members. Notwithstanding, in the way to put into practice quadruple helix model, some studies point out recently that a more proactive attitude regarding faculty and students, both undergraduate and graduate, could identify research results and conclusion papers, dissertation and theses with a high probability of application, thus creating an entrepreneurial culture and valuing technology transfer from the university [1].

2 STARTUP GARAGE

2.1 Concept

Startup Garage is an education and training space enlarging its boundaries, aimed at the interaction between students, teachers and enterprises, by jointly creating a formative laboratory, tailor-made to nurture cross-fertilization focusing on entrepreneurial ideas [6]. Startup Garage lets students apply knowledge to their ideas by helping four helix components to be intertwined differently.

Students coming up with good ideas are supported by teachers and researchers, who carry out the technical and scientific role of stand-by mentors, together with experts and managers of enterprises that play a sort of spur to make feasible ideas. In the middle, between teachers and enterprises, stands the Startup Garage Team that plays the role of tutoring, supported by young founders of start-ups as peers, ready to tell students about experiences they are lived out in the market. “Leo Student Circle” (Fig. 1) shows how entrepreneurial education system works, according to “Startup Garage Concept”, with the main and most important feature being the student as an active actor – innovation driver – surrounded by supporting figures.

Fig. 1 – Startup Garage Concept's accomplishment

The voluntary support of all the professional figures who revolve around the students creates an open and peaceful atmosphere, essential for living and learning to become entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurial students should be able to take useful skills in order to develop an aptitude for managing challenging issues and solve problems with creativity. In this sense, they could search for competent partners, shape the idea to generate interest in the market, understand the customer needs, manage the financial resources and build a team without being afraid of making mistakes. Jobs are dramatically changing, it is necessary to teach students to face any situation in an innovative and creative way.

2.2 Startup Garage within an academic environment

2.2.1 Entrepreneurial Student

The academic environment highlights and nurtures ideas from students as a continuous learning process. Nevertheless, entrepreneurship is not yet a transversal subject among all courses that students must have attended at the university to get his Bachelor's degree, Master's degree or Doctorate. Vocational universities certainly help students to find their way to put teachings into practice. Startup Garage encourages students to show their entrepreneurial ideas within an educational process. Startup Garage enables them to learn, both from a successful experience, and also from their own mistakes and failures. Mistakes moreover, as a frequent event, will be valued as an important learning opportunity.

2.2.2 Entrepreneurial Teacher

Around students a non-formal learning helix influences its outcome. Teachers are there to be facilitator; they are ready to be called by students for the startup ideas they are associated according to competence needs. That is why we call them stand-by mentors [6]. They help students to research and identify the right questions and find the best answers to doubts concerning their startup ideas.

Teachers, as stand-by mentors, have the opportunity to promote awareness about the startup idea feasibility, and by being involved in its progress, they could be caught up by young enthusiasm around it. They can keep their practice under constant review and adjust it in the light of desired learning outcomes and of the individual needs of students. We are still looking to enlarge the number of stand-by mentors as entrepreneurial teachers, who have a passion for teaching, are inspired, open-minded and confident, flexible and responsible — but also, from time to time, rule-breakers [7].

2.2.3 Enterprises as partner

Entrepreneurial competency and skills can be acquired or built only through hands-on, real life learning experiences [7]. In order to be always connected to the business reality, a particular importance is given to partnerships with the business community. Enterprises are invited to share their practical and professional experience with students, enabling them to put startup ideas and entrepreneurial skills into practice. Moreover, companies can invite students to help them to solve production problems, and to suggest implementation proposals.

This kind of co-operative process has led to develop an innovative transdisciplinary co-creation approach, with most principles based upon matching Open innovation 2.0, i.e. integrated collaboration, co-created shared value, cultivated innovation ecosystems, unleashed exponential technologies and extraordinarily rapid adoption [5]. In this sense, entrepreneurial students could help enterprises to put a plan into action and play an important role as “transfer vehicle” to spread creativity and innovation to medium-sized enterprises (SME).

Startup Garage Team has developed quite a large SME network soon to be part of an upgrading interaction system, in which they will be very involved within the Garage. At the same time, start-up experts and professional advisors will be asked to guide students “out of the Garage”, when they want to set up a start-up after their stay in the Garage.

2.3 From academic knowledge to entrepreneurial competences

Recently the “Startup Garage Concept” has been extended to contain a method to assess practical effectiveness of the concept. That was possible by taking into account *EntreComp User Guide* as a selective instrument to identify the competences that make students entrepreneurial [8]. Moreover, a raking classification of all startup ideas has been created by assigning a score.

A larger awareness about the importance of entrepreneurial learning has been raised. Faculty members have appraised and assessed entrepreneurship as a competence. Lately, Startup Garage Team has developed a digital assessment system to form up an “learning sheet” whose evaluation criteria rely very closely on “EntreComp three areas and 17 competences” as described and explained in European framework [8]. Entrepreneurial skills and attitudes can be monitored, recognized and assessed all along the non-formal learning process in the Startup Garage, following three steps (Figure 2). Effectively, once startup ideas are discovered and retained, successful applicants can work on them supported by Startup Garage Team management. During the first learning step, creative and visionary students identify real needs related to their ideas, so as to develop business opportunities. They explore solution to new challenges in a fast changing market. Once the potential of startup ideas is recognized, second step will lead students to check their ideas with limited resources provided. Proof-of-concepts are planned. Peers, teammates, active mentors are there to help them. Students are facing with cost budgeting in order to develop prototypes and marketing surveys. They team up with other students and let their ideas to be known by sectorial experts in individual and common meetings. If admitted, students will experiment a challenging third step, which is devoted to validate startup ideas by testing prototypes. Once self-confident, students draw up professional business plan. They are ready to present their startup ideas outside. They go into action. Eventually, students will show entrepreneurship as a competence for life, which help them certainly, both to find a job, and to set up a start-up business.

Fig. 2 – Apply EntreComp wheel in the non-formal Startup Garage learning process

3 STARTUP IDEAS AND THE MARKET

For pre-revenue businesses, as idea startups are, need a proven defined concept to build a strong position to demonstrate their future profitability and protect the intellectual property. If entrepreneurial students have a patentable idea, they may raise angel investment to formally

fulfill the patent application. The people involved in a business have been shown to be the most significant aspect for angel investors when deciding to make an investment, taking into consideration their experience, skills, drive, and the impression they make. They will then of course look carefully at the business itself and the core aspects of the business plan.

4 PINGEL@P

A digital platform is specifically developed to organize activities offered around the students with startup ideas (see “Leo Student Circle” in Fig.1). It continues to develop by taking into account changing needs from stakeholders and the increasing demand to protect IP. Pingel@p, assists with the collection and assessment of startup ideas and in particular matches entrepreneurial students with teacher stand-by mentors. An algorithm associates an idea with a potential to the most suited stand-by mentor, mainly on the basis of the needs expressed in the idea description, the competences declared by the stand-by mentors, and according to industry sectors. Three main parameters are required to be evaluated on an idea by a mentor: technological feasibility, innovation items, and business potential breakthrough.

After the assessment, a general ranking of startup ideas is produced. Every year, only a number of submitted ideas are retained and admitted as startup ideas in the Startup Garage (see Fig. 2). Once the assessment and admission process is ended, students will know their voluntary teacher at disposal as an active mentor. Thereafter, every step forward in developing startup ideas will be “certified” by a new “learning assessment”, which “measures” entrepreneurial knowledge acquisition on the basis of relevant elements extrapolated from EntreComp framework. In order to satisfy increasing inputs coming from enterprises’ partner, thanks to Pingel@p they will soon be profiled and classified in order to assign them with an active role to encourage entrepreneurship. As enterprises associated to Startup Garage they have right to “call for needs resolution” awaiting entrepreneurial students to help them.

4.1 IP and Blockchain

Recently “Startup Garage Concept” has been extended to contain a method to exploit blockchain for Intellectual Protection (IP). Since the first implementation of the repository, idea ownership has been safeguarded after their insertion by recording a timestamp of the first reading of the idea description by any user (e.g. stand-by mentor). An agreement is presented in a disclaimer stating the terms of use of the accessed content, establishing a sort of contract. Blockchain technology has been used in a lot of different context and applied also to protect intellectual property, such as for example in the Design Thinking process, where a unique hash is generated from each digital artifact and digitally stored into a blockchain network to guarantee both proof-of-existence and proof-of-origin [9].

Effectively, blockchain technology establishes ownership via a decentralized ledger that consists of a short description of the nature and goal of the invention according to the idea structure in Pingel@p, where a user would then have to accept the provisions of an agreement (“smart contract”) to gain access to more information on the invention works. A further step towards a stronger intellectual property protection has been recently accomplished through

blockchain smart contracts. It is very hard to corrupt to system, and makes it easy to record the ownership of “smart contracts”. This mechanism is used here to protect ideas and it is implemented as a software module (in progress) integrated in the Pingel@p web application on the server side in Java. The rationale behind blockchain adoption for idea farming protection is supported by the fact that while companies usually have lawyers to defend their intellectual property, small inventors do not have many options to create an indelible record of their authorship.

5 NON FORMAL LEARNING

5.1 Concept

A new concept has been introduced into the Garage to apply knowledge in an intertwined and interconnected pattern of collaborative entrepreneurial education. The innovative idea puts together three different categories of participants: students, stand-by mentors, employees and managers. It will blend innovation and business spirit, thus reducing the gap between academics’ constraints and business’ needs. Students have great enthusiasm and creative spirit, but less organizational and business experience; stand-by mentors have high and specialized technical competence and a scientific approach, but low business experience; manager and employees have high performance and experience in business organization, but low access to top research. According to main requested skills, students may learn to be entrepreneur thanks to an education method managed to: encourage the cross fertilization of skills and competences; transmit entrepreneurial skills; motivate multidisciplinary teams; learning by doing implementing an idea in mixed groups during the training course. It comes out that a new course “tailored-made” has been introduced: *The enterprise of an Idea* (3 ECTS). It is addressed to students holding a startup idea, to stand-by mentors and employees and managers of enterprises. Every participant can choose topics his own interests and his startup idea’s state of development such as: inspiration and validity innovation, team work, product management, patent and legal aspects, accounting, financing, marketing and digital marketing, networking and pitch. In addition, Startup Garage team arranges almost every informal meeting (*Business Cakes*) in order to let students assess the feasibility of their startup ideas by critical peer-to-peer interactions. A multi-disciplinary way of thinking at their business.

6 PERFORMANCE EVOLUTION

An important indicator has been developed – Entrepreneurial Willingness Rate (EWR) – in a way to evaluate how many students out of a total of new students enrolled, show interest during the annual “call for ideas”. They have participated by applying through the ICT digital platform.

EWR has been specified in two different statistical indicators:

- EWR restrained (EWR_{re}), by taking into account all students who have personally submitted an idea (applicants) out of total new students enrolled;
- EWR extended (EWR_{ex}) by considering the number of students (team mates) – who have joined teams built by successful startups – out of total new students enrolled.

It results in the following statistical figures:

- Both EWRre and EWRex are quite impressive compared to a small reality and business environment: on average more than 10% of our students show over three years considered (2018, 2019, 2020) some entrepreneurial aptitude if scouted;
- Significant increase of the quality of the new startup ideas in terms of scientific and technical feasibility (number of retained ideas out of total submitted ideas);
- Applicants seem to prefer to submit new ideas individually and not, as previously, collectively; however, they have learned the importance of team work, because they are ready to enlarge teams during their stay in the Garage by exploiting the IT Pingel@p service “call for expertise” to find out students willing to help them;
- Significant percentage of voluntary teachers taking part as voluntary Stand-by Mentors: 25% on average of the total faculty members over three years considered.

Fig. 3 – Trends in the Startup Garage

Emerging trends are surprisingly interesting, so persuading Startup Garage Team to keep managing all the process on a voluntary basis as done so far. It should be pursued with common and profitable perspectives for each stakeholder involved in spreading out the Startup Garage Concept and its realizing process.

1 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

With Startup Garage, a step forward is made to empower the theoretical *quadruple helix* model. Starting from students, ideas flow across disciplines and stakeholders to become common values in a co-creation ecosystem. Combined with human competences and expertise, startup ideas are innovation inputs moving a dynamic process, an open system in which all stakeholders benefit because of common-purpose-driven actions.

As up-to-date consumer-driven subjects, students today are best fitted to create innovative products featuring new markets and services. Effectively, “Startup Garage Concept” leads entrepreneurial students to free up ideas from an internal state of mind, whose inputs are still, but ready to work if only stimulated. For this purpose, SMEs are soon going to act as a catalyst in asking students to implement/invent something new for them. An open window will be planned to let enterprises “*call for needs resolution*”. Students must be seen as an active subject, open-minded, potentially disruptive, different from a passive object, whose heads are there to be filled up.

Students can exploit classical theoretical-scientific instruments and knowledge, they gradually obtain during their curricula, into a stimulating practical adventure. In fact, students are encouraged to develop their own entrepreneurial ideas as an educational process, so interacting with both the academic knowledge and the business dynamics. In this process students receive objective feedbacks that can enable them to learn and evolve not only from their successful experiences, but also primarily from their own mistakes and failures

A quite large enterprise network will be soon integrated in the interaction system, in which SME, especially, should be much more involved within the Garage. At the same time, both start-up experts and professional advisors would be asked to guide students “out of the Garage” (Step out Guidance), if they want to set up a real start-up after having overcome steps in the Garage during their studies.

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